

"Relentless focus on implementation of worker's Participation in management for The growth and development of Industry or organisation " A case study of Tata Iron and Steel Co. Ltd. (TISCO) Jharkhand.

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Abstract – Ours age is an age of management. it plays vital role of development of any Industry or organisations. This research paper explores role of worker's. Participation in management and its emplementation in Indian Industry for the growth and development of Industry. Worker's Participation in management is also main part of Human resource management. worker's participations in management is mainly based on democratic thinking and principles. Worker's Participation in management is not a specific technique but rather a concept of management. which advocate employees having voice in decission making process. In many countries like England, Sweden, Germany and U.S.A etc, In this field a lot of research works have been done. and support the significance of W.P.M.. Worker's participation in management was introduce in India in the year 1920. When Mahatama Gandhi suggested that workers should participate and contribute to the organisation and also share its prosperity with the increased participation of subordinate. The management should develop positve approach and favourable attitude to the participative management. It is hoped that Industry organisation can be certainly developed.

Keywords – Concept of W.P.M., Role of W.P.M, Causes and Failure of W.P.M & Relentless focus on implementation of worker's participation in management for growth and development, TISCO.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ours age is an age of management. This study is based on reviewing the possition of workers participations in management in Tata Iron and Steel Company Ltd. It plays vital role of development any industry or organisation. This research paper explores role of worker's,

Participation in management for the growth and development of industry. W.P.M is main part of Human resource management. Worker's participation in management is mainly based on democratic thinking and principles. Worker's participation in management refers sharing the decision making power with the lower level workers by the top level management in organisation. This concept is orginated from the word or Democracy . It is the process of management of the people, for the people and by the people, It gives a sense of belonging among the worker towards the organisation.

" Comming together is a begining"
" Keeping together is a progress " and
" Working together is a sucess"

Aboue the quotation said by "Henery Ford' it signifies for workers to influence the managerial decision making process at different level by various forms in the organisation. It authorises the workers to take part in the managerial process. Worker's participation in management is not a specific technique but rather a concept of management which advocates employees having a voice in the decision making process. W.P.M introduces in India in the year 1920, when Mahatma Gandhi had suggested that workers should participates and contribute to the organisations and also share itt prosperity.

Tata Iron and steel com Ltd. - Tata Iron and Steel Co. Ltd. was established on 26th Augutst 1907 at sakshi in the district of singhbhum in the state of Jharkhand. Now this time it is known as Tata Steel Com Ltd. Tata Steel Company Continuously success without any break day after day and year after year due to up to date technology. Managerial excelance, W.P.M, Leadership stylen and employees satisfaction sarvey.

Objective of the study: There are the following main objective of this research work

- To analyze concept of W.P.M.
- To anylyze role of W.P.M.
- To analyse causes and failure of W.P.M.
- To analyze relentless focus on implementation of W.P.M
- A case of study of TISCO.

Research Methodology:- There are the following research methodology is used for this research work.

- **Primary data:-** In this research work all material collected from Tisco and management Training Institute Jamsedpur.
- **Secondary data:-** In this research was work all material collected from books, magzine and journal published by the Tisco.

II. TO ANALYSE CONCEPT OF WPM

Participation in management is not a specific Technique but rather a concept of management which advocates employees having voice in the decesion making process. In

study to determine how executives viewed participative management. Larry Greiner Found that despite the rather abstract concept of participative approach, no matter what their particular managerial technique, most of the respondents viewed certain elements as always being present before participative leadership. Exist As shown in the figure 6.1 the act of following subordinates to share in decision making was ranked the highest among the participation characteristics.

Rank Average scale rating

1. Given subordinates a share in decision making	6.08
2. Keeps subordinate of the true situation, good or bad under all circumstances	5.69
3. Satisfies aware of the state of the organisation " Morale and does everything possible to make it high	5.45
4. Is easily approachable	5.38
5. Counsels, trains and develops subordinates	5.34
6. Communicates effectively with subordinate	5.22
7. Shows thoughtfulness and consideration	5.19
8. Is willing to make changes in ways of doing things	4.96
9. Is willing to support subordinates even when they make mistakes	4.92
10. Expresses appreciation when a subordinate does a good job.	4.80

Above the figure shows ten highest participation characteristics. The 6.08 rating given this characteristics of participation is an average of responses where 7 was equal to high participation and 1 equal to low participation. The foundation of participative concept is more participation of employees in the management function. this can be by the nature of attributes listed in figure 6.1. this attributes are major elements in the success of the participative style of leadership and can be related to the discussion of the determinants of leadership styles in the participation process.

The participation feature represents subordinate expectancies indicate/signifies

What a manager must do to be successful in a participative approach. The ability to incorporate these traits in to leadership styles would create an environment. which would reinforce, employee involvement and encourages further participation with the in increased. participation of subordinate it is hoped that following result will be.

- The manager will be free of some less important tasks and thus will be able to spend more time, on more important matters.
- When employees have a vested in decisions they will be their utmost to see, that the decision is carried out in the best possible manner.

Of course the key to any successful participative method is the people of the organisation. So it can be said WPM plays vital role of success of any Industry.

II. Role of worker's participation in management. We know that very well, WPM is elastic concept. Before the

explanation of role of WPM at first we will discuss about W.P.M and then after we will discuss about role of worker's participation in management.

(i) worker's participation in management:-

Worker's participation in management means sharing the decision making power by the top level management to the lower level management in the organisation. W.P.M introduced in India in the year 1920, when Mahatma Gandhi suggested that worker should participate and contribute to the organisation and also share its in prosperity. When the management give an opportunity to the worker participate in the management, They take great interest in his work certainly productivity and efficiency of the worker may be increased.

It is very difficult to define WPM because different learner define its different way.

According to Keith Devis workers' participation refers to the mental and emotional involvement of a person in a group situation which encourages him to contribute to group goals and share in responsibility of achieving them"

Allport (1945) refers to " participation in decision as active involvement. According to Davis (1997) participation may be defined as the mental and emotional involvement of a person in a group situation which encourage him to contribute goals share responsibilities in them" .

Batteriet Butteriss (1971) describes participatives as process where by workers have share in the reaching of managerial decision in the Enterprises"

(ii) Role of Worker's Participation in Management :-

Worker's participation in management plays significance role of development of any Industry worker's participation in management is one of the most important elements of industrial democracy. It is a such system where employees have a say in the decision of management. This has an incredibly positive impact in the mental and psychological health of the workers and they are associated with the organisation. WPM focus on sharing power with worker who are engaged in work rather than being concentrating on one hand. Main role of WPM to develop loyalty and trust and towards, the organisation and have a positive impact on the productivity of employee.

When the management or an organisation to give an opportunity to the workers/labour or lower level management to participate in the Managerial decision, in this case workers very satisfied and they take great interest in his work due to this reason organisation/Industry achieved business goal certainly. So it can be said role of workers participation in management play vital role of development of any organisation. Workers participation in management has been successful in some of the organisation like, TISCO, BHEL and Maruti Udyog Ltd. For the meaningful participation of workers in the organisation which help the organisations in various way in to allow workers in all the decision level. it will help the workers to feel the following -

- A better understanding of their role,
- A sense of belongingness.
- Satisfy the urge.
- Stimulate their interest in higher productivity sethi, K (1973).

Worker's participation in management is basically an effective method to avoid industrial disputes which are less likely to happen if implemented and followed successfully.

III. REASON OF FAILURE OF WPM IN INDIA

WPM is needed in the interest of worker and management. Despite it the state of affairs of WPM is not encouraging in India. Following factors have been responsible behind the failure of WPM in India, management is not responsible due to emphasis on freedom to decide. Autocratic attitude is a major hurdle. Even educated managers have a gap between their advocacy and reality. Due to poor experience of democratic working, class consciousness. Manager failed in providing participation union and workers are also responsible due to inter union rivalry faction within unions, outside leadership and lack of union democracy.

Workers lacking education, vocational skills and commitment can not support participation for economically poor workers earning for livelihood in the main goal. WPM is a luxury political system is also responsible for failure in making momentum and will need to pass WPM bill.

Hence, WPM could not become a way of Industrial life, in addition! Industries, it is in a poor state.

There are the following other main reasons of failure of WPM.

- There is a lack of following up measures.
- A majority of workers in India are not strongly motivated to assume decision making responsibility.
- Management lacks a positive response to the idea of worker participation.
- In India trade unions are not very strong and responsible.
- More emphasis has been given to participation at the shop level.
- Not co-operative attitude of workers.
- Concept of WPM is not clear.
- Legal definition, Scope and function of WPM not clear.
- No strong trade union.

IV. RELENTLESS FOCUS ON IMPLEMENTATION OF WPM

After Independence of India several schemes introduced by the government to promote worker's participation in India. There are the following schemes

- **Mill Committees:-** Textile Industry in India is the oldest industry. The employees in the textile industry encouraged joint consultation with the workers by establishing mill committees, which were empowered to represent grievance of workers.
- **Royal Commission in Labour:-** The government of India in 1920 constituted a joint committee, in their printing press and Railways. During the same period such committees were formed in TISCO, Jamshedpur. At the instance of Mahatma Gandhi, the workers of the textile mills at Ahmedabad agreed in 1920 mutual discussion and consultation of issues facing which they were to be resolved by arbitration.

From 1922 onwards, joint committees of worker and management were formed in Bengal, Madras and other states. After observing the performance of such committees, The Royal Commission on Labour found the same committees have been successful and there are few that have been disappointing. The reasons assigned by the committee were lack of clarity with the management and trade unions and illiteracy of the Indian. iii. Works committee, iv. Joint management council workers. Workers director 1970, shop and joint council 1975-1977, The new scheme 1984.

The 1990 parliamentary bill :- The government of India introduced a bill in parliament on June 25, 1990, as a remedy to the failure of all the schemes of the organisational level. This bill suggested meaningful three-tier participation to the workers in management at three levels: shop floor, organisation and board level. This also provided the principle of secret ballot for choosing representative of workers.

The scheme of worker participation in management has been successful in some of the organisations like BHEL, TESCO, SAIL and Maruti Udyog, etc.

In the organisation or industry workers and management should be treated equally. Now this time it is very necessary to focus relentlessly on implementation of worker participation in management for the growth and development of industry.

Recently the Government of India introduced a similar participatory governance scheme. The Honourable Prime Minister launched my government on 26th July 2014. My government is a government of India citizens engaged platform. It works with numerous government organisations and ministries to involve citizens in the policy making process and solicit their opinion on matters and subjects that they are important to the welfare of the general public. Participatory governance is based on citizens' involvement in voice in policy formation. The youth is the backbone of my government outreach platform. My government facilitates participatory governance or Janbhagidari. The Honourable Prime Minister emphasised participatory governance for all-around development of our country. Its positive effect can be seen currently the platform has over 2.5 crores registered users, and over 10 to 15 crores citizens engaged via social media daily.

V. WORKER'S PARTICIPATION IN MANAGEMENT OF TATA STEEL

Worker's participation in management is a concept shrouded with so much vagueness that for different people it has different meanings. The term has been used in a variety of senses and has come to be associated with varying practices in different countries. The practice of different countries differ in respect of range of subjects handled by participation machinery, in the degree of authority exercised with regard to these subjects, and in the methods of selection of worker's representative. Notwithstanding these differences, worker's participation in management is crystallization of the notion of industrial democracy. It is an expression of the employer's desire to bind his employees into a team working together toward a common purpose. When the system is used to the full advantage of both partners, blue collar worker are no longer just workers; they become the lowest level of management. Because the company needs fewer administrators to supervise them, it can fashion a leaner and more responsive organization, with clearer and faster communication up and down the chain.

The Workers' Participation in the management of Tata Steel has economic, psychological, social and ethical objectives. Its economic objective is to increase workers productivity. This is possible only through fullest co-operation between labour and management for poor labour management relations which do not encourage the worker to give more than the minimum necessary to retain the job and that, in many cases, is all he gives. The psychological objective of the scheme is to raise workers' level of motivation. This is made possible under the scheme through the satisfaction of his non-economic needs.

Participation provides the workers with a sense of importance, pride and accomplishment, freedom and opportunity for expression, a feeling of belonging to the place of work and a sense of workmanship and creativity. Socially, the need for participation arises because modern industry is a social institution with the interests of the capital owner, the employer, the community and the workers equally vested in it. Participation forges ties of understanding between the two principal groups leading to better effort and harmony all round and its absence introduces a sullenness in behavior which ultimately may flare up into a conflict with consequential suffering and inconvenience to the society in general. The ethical objective of participation is to develop workers free personality and to recognize human dignity.

According to Keith Davis, a most popular Social Scientist, participation may be defined as mental and emotional involvement of a person in a group situation, which encourages him to contribute to group goals and share responsibility in them. There are three important ideas in this definition: (i) Participation mean mental and emotional involvement rather than mere physical activity. Some managers mistake physical involvement for true

participation, which is wrong. (ii) Participation motivates a person to make his own contribution toward the objectives of the organization. In this way, participation differs from "consent". The consenters do not contribute; they merely approve. Participation is more than getting consent for something already decided. (iii) Participation encourages a person to accept responsibility in the group's activities. It is a social process, which makes an individual speak in terms of "we" and not "they". He is ready to work actively with other members of his team, instead of reactively against them.

Several research studies have also shown that the intensity of participation depends on four factors: (a) the subject matter of decision- making ; (b) the level of decision-making; (c) the personal characteristics of the individuals who are asked to participate in the decision- making; and (d) the stage of participation.

(a) Subject- matter of Decision-making:- By and large, the workers' interest in participation varies with the nature of issues involved in decision. Workers show greatest interest in those issues, which affect their socio-economic status and show least interest in those issues, which concern relations outside the enterprises.

(b) Level of Participation:- Level of participation is another factor, which determines the interest of workers in participation as such. Studies have revealed that most workers' desire control over their day-to-day work and the decision, which affect it. In other words, it is at their workplace that workers feel they have the knowledge to contribute and not at higher levels.

Participation can be take place at four levels in enterprises. These are: job level, management level, policy-making level and ownership level. Participation at the job level is mostly informal. Here, the supervisor and his immediate group sit together on an adhoc basis to consider problems about the work, delegation of authority and so on. Participation at the management level generally takes place though the mechanism of consultative committees or some other joint bodies consisting of management and worker's representative. These bodies share information and decision-making on several important issues such as planning, coordination and control of work, conditions under which work is done and so on. At the policy-making level, participation takes place by appointing workers' representatives on the company's board of directors, which takes all key decisions on investments, new venture, expansion, etc. At the ownership level, participation may imply a share in the equity, which is not meaningful unless the workers have sufficient control through voting rights to determine the composition of the board.

(c) Personal Characteristics:- Workers' interest in participation is also influenced by certain personal or group characteristics. For example, there is generally positive correlation between intensity of involvement of workers and their level of education. Factors like sex and age have also been found to influence workers' participation.

(d) Stage of Participation:- There are three successive stages before one can reach the final stage of participation. These are : (a) Communication, i.e. sharing of information with the workers about all decisions taken by the management; (b) consultation, i.e. jointly executing the views of the workers before the decisions are taken; (c) Collaboration, i.e. jointly executing the decisions taken by the management; and (d) Co-determination, i.e. taking joint decisions by the management and the workers in social, personnel and financial areas in that order.

There is now a growing realization in several countries of the world that management is too important to be left to managers alone and that workers' participation in management is one of the Directive Principles of State Policy embodied in Article- 43A of our constitution. This Article provides:

The State Shall take steps, by suitable legislation, or in any other way, to secure the participation of workers in the management of undertakings, establishments or other organizations engaged in any industry. Several experiments have been made for time to give effect to this constitutional imperative. A brief description of these experiments in their chronological order is given below.

The first experiment began in 1947 when the Industrial Disputes Act was passed. The Act provides that in the case of any industrial establishment in which 100 or more worker are employed on any day in the preceding 12 month, the appropriate Government may by general or special order require the employer to constitute in the prescribed manner a works Committee consisting of representative of employers and workmen engaged in the establishment, so, however, that the number of representative of the workmen on the committee shall not be less than the number of representatives of the employer. The representatives of the workmen shall be chosen in the prescribed manner from among the workmen engaged in the establishment and in consultation with their trade union, if any, registered under the Indian trade unions Act, 1926. it shall be the duty of the Works committee to promote measures for securing and preserving unity and good relations between the employer and workmen and, to that end to comment upon matters of their common interest or concern and endeavour to compose any material difference of opinion in respect of such matters.

Despite their numerical growth, Works Committee have not proved very much effective. Often the vagueness in the legal definition of the scope and functions of these committees has come in the way of their effectiveness. To remedy the defect, the Indian labour Conference drew up in 1959 an illustrative list of items, such as, (i) conditions of work such as ventilation, lighting, temperature and sanitation including latrins and urinals; (ii) Amenities such as drinking water, canteens, dining rooms, medical and health services; (iii) safety and accident prevention, occupational diseases and protective equipment; (iv) Adjustment of festival and national holydays; (v) Administration of welfare and fine funds;

(vi) educational and recreational activities; (vii) Promotion of thrift and savings; and (viii) Implementation and review of decisions arrived at in the meetings of Works Committees, which these committees could deal with. The item excluded from the purview of the committees were: wages and allowance, bonus and profit-sharing, rationalization and work- load, fixation of a standard labour force, programmes of planning and development, retrenchment and lay-off, victimization for trade union activities, retirement benefits, provident fund and gratuity, quantum of leave and holidays, incentive schemes and housing and transport services.

Although the above clarifications about the scope and functions have proved generally helpful but there are numerous other difficulties, which have led to the failure of these committees. these are as under:

- there is lack of interest among workers due to assignment of minor functions to the Works Committees and exclusion of issues such as wages and allowances, bonus, rationalization, retrenchment, lay-off, etc. from the purview of these committees;
- There is lack of competence shown by the workers representative on these committees;
- Some employers consider these committees as substitutes for collective bargaining and, therefore, bypass the unions. Hence the unions view these committees as a threat to their very existence and in such apprehension lose every interest in their constitution;
- Some employers insist upon their prerogatives and consider it below their dignity to sit on these committees with their employees;
- Inter-union rivalries, absence of provision to hold the election of representative by secret ballot or to recall a member who forfeits the confidence of the workers in general are also reasons responsible for the ineffectiveness of these committees; and
- The recommendation of these committees are advisory in nature and there is mostly delay in their implementation. This also dampens the enthusiasm of the workers to make Works Committees successful.

The second experiment in participative management began in 1958 with the establishment of joint management Councils. These came into existence as a result of our acceptance of the socialistic pattern of society as the goal (1954); Indian Labour Conference recommendation to encourage participation workers in Industry (1955); the industrial policy Resolution statement that in a socialist democracy "labour is a partner in the common task of development and should participate in it with enthusiasm" (1956); and the Second Five Year plan's observation that for the successful implementation of the plan "increased association of labour with management is necessary". The immediate causes were the report of a tripartite Study Group, which went to Europe and recommended a scheme

for participative management (1957) and a model agreement regarding establishment of such councils (1958).

It was decided that Joint Management Councils should consist of an equal number of representatives of the management and employees, not exceeding 12 and should be set up at the plant level on a voluntary basis in selected industrial units. The criteria laid down for the selection of industrial units were: (i) the undertaking should employ at least 500 workers,

(ii) it should have a well established, strong and representative workers' union affiliated to some central organization, and (iii) the undertaking must be one with a good record of industrial relations. These councils are required to work at the policy level without encroaching upon the field of Works Committees. The essential functions of joint Management Council are as under:

- The Council is to be consulted by the management on administration of standing orders, introduction of new methods of production and closure, reduction in or cessation of production;
- The council has the right to receive information, discuss and give suggestions on general economic situation, state of the market, production and sales programmes, organization and general running of the concern, methods of manufacture and work, annual balance sheet and profit and loss statement and long-term plans for expansion, redevelopment, etc.
- The Council is to be entrusted with the responsibility in respect of administration of welfare measures, supervision of safety measures, vocational training, apprenticeship scheme, schedules of working hours, breaks and holidays and rewards for suggestions.

Issues relating to wages, bonuses etc., which are subjects for collective bargaining, are excluded from the scope of the councils. Individual grievances are also excluded from the purview of the discussion. despite the useful purpose, the joint Management Council could serve, in many cases they are reported to be ineffective and their functioning unsatisfactory. The scheme is voluntary and has been adopted by only a limited number of undertakings in the public and private sectors. The reasons for their unsatisfactory working are as under:

1. Workers' representative on these councils feel dissatisfied with their role as decision-makers in respect of welfare activities only They want to be given authority to share decisions on more important subjects of collective bargaining like wages and bonus in which they say the workers are most keenly interested.
2. Trade unions fear that the joint Management Councils where the workers are likely to be more amenable to the influence of the employers would weaken unions' hold over the workers.
3. There is also an apprehension that the workers' not having the expertise for management, are likely to be

at a disadvantage vis-à-vis the management when complex matters are discussed.

4. management is often not prepared to give as much information to the workers' as they need for proper decision-making.
5. Middle Management and Supervisors are generally hostile to workers' participation because they resent their actions being questioned on the shop floor. The fact that the management sometimes sides with the workers' representatives and reprimands the supervisors weakens their authority.
6. Employers who already have the system of consultation with their workers in the form of Workers Committees and the recognized unions find the joint management Councils in their present form quite superfluous.
7. There is inherent contradiction between the role of union leaders at the bargaining table where they can put all kinds of pressure on management and their role as members of a joint council when they must subordinate their sectional interests to those of an undertaking as a whole.
8. The absence of a representative union has made it difficult for the Council to work smoothly.

The majority view of the National Commission on Labour was that these joint Management Council were yet another bipartite consultative forum at the plant level, which served no useful purpose and therefore, their functions could be amalgamated with the functions of Works Committees. The INTUC members of the Commission, however, disagreed with this view. They argued that while the Works Committee was a statutory requirement, it was confined to minor problems of a day-to-day nature arising in the course of a plant, whereas joint Management Council was a voluntary arrangement and functioned on a much higher level with a far wider scope and higher objectives, beyond the reach of the Works Committee. They asserted that the upland of the joint Management Council was beyond the gaze of any Works Committee.

On 30th October 1975 the Central Government adopted through a resolution a new scheme of Workers' participation in Management. This scheme was also voluntary like the 1958 scheme. The scheme covered all manufacturing and mining industries (whether in public, private or cooperative sector, including departmentally run enterprises) employing 500 or more persons.

(v) Safety measures:

(vi) Assistance in maintain general discipline in the shop/department;

(vii) Physical conditions of working, such as, lighting, ventilation, noise, dust, etc, and reduction of fatigue;

(viii) Welfare and health measures to be adopted for efficient running of the shop/department; and

(ix) Ensuring proper flow of adequate two-way communication between the management and the workers, particularly on matters relating to production figures, production schedules and progress in achieving the targets. Joint Council :

In every industrial unit employing 500 or more workers, there was to be joint Council for the whole unit. The main features and the functions of the Joint Council were as follows:

Main features of Joint council:

1. Only such persons who are actually engaged in the unit shall be members of the Joint Council;
2. The Council shall function for a period of two years;
3. The Chief Executive of the unit shall be the Chairman of the Joint Council; there shall be a Vice- Chairman who will be nominated by worker-members of the Council;
4. The Joint Council shall appoint one of the members of the Council as its Secretary. Necessary facilities for the efficient discharge of functions by the Secretary shall be provided within the premises of the undertaking/establishment;
5. The term of the Council, once formed, shall be for a period of two years; if, however, a member is nominated in the mid-term of the Council to fill a casual vacancy, the member nominated in such vacancy shall continue in office for the remaining period of the term of the Council;
6. The Joint Council shall meet at least once in a quarter;
7. Every decision of the Joint Council shall be on the basis of consensus and not by a process of voting and shall be binding on employers and workmen and shall be implemented within one month unless otherwise stated in the decision itself.

• Functions of Joint Council :

The Joint Council was to deal with matters relating to:

1. Optimum production, efficiency and fixation of productivity norms of man and machine for the unit as a whole;
2. Functions of a Shop Council, which have a bearing on another shop or the unit as a whole;
3. Matters emanating from Shop councils, which remain unresolved;
4. Work planning and achieving production targets, more specifically, tasks assigned to a shop Council at the shop/department level but relevant to the unit as a whole;
5. The development of skill of workmen and adequate facilities for training;
6. The preparation of schedules of working hours and of holidays;
7. Awarding of rewards for valuable and creative suggestions received from workers;
8. Optimum use of raw materials and quality of finished products;
9. General health, welfare and safety measures for the unit or the plant.

No uniform pattern was laid down under the scheme of the constitution of shop Councils and Joint Councils, particularly relating to the representation of workers. The

management, in consultation with workers, was to evolve the most suitable pattern of representation so as to ensure that the representation of the workers resulted in effective, meaningful and broad- based participation of workers. The Works Committees, as prescribed under the Industrial Disputes Act, were to continue to function in addition to this scheme.

Workers' Participation in the Management of Tata Steel:

Tata Steel provides a refreshing example of workers' participation in the management. The company has a three-tier set up: Joint Department Councils (JDCs) for each department of the works, Joint Works Council (JWC) for the entire works and Joint Consultative Council of Management (JCCM) at the apex. JDCs, which meet twice a month study at their departmental levels several issues, such as , increase in productivity, elimination of waste, reduction of cost, reduction in absenteeism, improvement in working conditions, promotion of welfare and safety and so on. JWC reviews every month the working of JDCs, JCCM meets once in a quarter and considers questions referred to it by the JWC and advises management on economic and financial matters. As a result of this scheme the company has been able to achieve.

- Over 100% efficiency in its operations in spite of its ageing plants;
- A ready-made forum for cross fertilization and fast communication of ideas;
- An unique distinction of more than 75 years of harmonious industrial relations;
- Emergence of a cadre of well-informed and enlightened trade union leaders from the grass roots
- Spirit of brotherhood and a high sense of commitment.

VI. FINDING CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

After a through study of the above subject matter we reached at the certain points the worker's participation in management plays vital role of development of any Industry or organization. Worker's participation in management is one of the most important elements of industrial democracy. WPM focus on sharing power with Worker's who are engaged in work rather than being can concentrating on one hand. When the management gives an opportunity to worker/labour to participate in the managical decision in this case workers very satisfied and they take great in his work due to this reason industry achieved business goal certainly. So it can be said worker participation in management is necessary for the industrial growth and development. The Industrial policy resolution of 1948 also supported the Participation of worker's in all level.

The government of India Set up a "Study Group on WPM" in 1956 and examined a study on wpm in other Countries and submitted a report with the recommendation that implementation of wpm on voluntary basis and sub committee should be developed for emplementation of

wpm in India. The Government of India makes amendment in constitution of India Wpm as a directive principle of State Policy. All the scheme/efforts of Government of India for the meaningful participation of workers in management. Thus government introduced a bill in parliament failed 25 th May 1990. The bill proposes the participation at all the levels but they also it failed. If the worker's are involved in the decision making process, they tend to perceive it more beneficial for themselves.

During the time of changes in the organization such as adaption of new technology, at the times of pandemic, changes in government policies or during the time recession there should be increase in the participation of workers.

There is the following suggestion for implementation of w.p.m in Industry/organization.

- Proper implementation of wpm in all Sector as like private sector and public sector.
- Objectives of w.p.m should be clear.
- Worker is the backbone of Industrial development.
- W.P.M is the key to achieving equitable and Sustainable goal.

- There should be a democratic strong and representatives union of worker's to participate in management in behalf of workers.
- The workers and management should develop positive approach and favorable attitude to participative management.
- The government should set up special vigilance department for monitering participatory Governance and worker's participation in management in India.
- To avoid pseudo worker's participation in management.
- WPM is legal right of the workers so Industries should facility to participate in management for increasing efficiency and productivity of the employee.
- The government should relentless focus on implementation of wpm and participatory Governance for development of our country.
- The management of Tata steel company shuld have more respossive attitud Towards the workers.
- The trade union should be strong and should fully suport the idea of worker's participation in management.
- The management should give more freedom to employees of the organisation to take part in the management of Tata Iron Steel Company Ltd.

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